

Social Challenges and Sustainable Family Living in an Unstable Economy

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Introduction

The world today and Nigeria is passing through a lot of social and environmental challenges that is affecting her economy hence the concept of sustainable family living in an unstable economy. An unstable economy portrays a state of financial crisis characterized with fluctuations in the country's economic activities and fortunes. It is characterized with unemployment, public fear, homelessness, starvation, insecurity, poverty, lack of confidence by the citizenry, lower rates of investments and spending, inflations which lead to higher prices and anger among consumers and businessmen and women, lack of access to health care, problems with childcare, poor housing facilities, poor nutrition amongst others.

The citizens of any nation are basically members of a family unit hence to the African, a family is a social group of people who come from the same ancestors, living together and consists of parents and their children, aunts, uncles, cousins, grandparents, in-laws among others. To some Europeans, a family is limited to father, mother, and children. In a period of an unstable economy, members of family households face lots of challenges that force them to seek ways of embracing sustainable family living practices. Sustainable living, therefore, involves sustained efforts to reducing demands and consumptions of natural and human resources in order to

maximize their use to the benefits of family members.

Our society today has been plagued with some social challenges that make sustainable family living difficult among various households. Such challenges include-family resource management, family health and lifestyle, family crisis and insecurity, food security and nutrition, Covid-19 pandemic and family adjustment and trend in fashion and sustainable clothing innovation. This paper therefore focuses on the above sub-themes with a view of finding solutions to enhancing them in a depressed economy.

Family Resource Management in an Unstable Economy

For a family to be happy and healthy in any unstable economy, the issue of her resource management must be taken with every sense of concern. The provision and management of both her human and material resources must be geared towards the benefit of every family member. Family Resource Management is therefore the planning, organizing, evaluating, and controlling of both human and material resources available to family members in order to accomplish their set goals, meet their needs, improve their quality of life and achieve happy and healthy family living. This demands that family members not only apply their physical strengths, but they are also to be creative, exhibit entrepreneurial skills and judicious

in using all available resources. To have sustainable living, family members should prioritize the use of their natural and renewable resources while avoiding creating excessive waste and depleting resources for their descendants. Family Resource Management and Sustainable Living in an unstable economy involve effective fruitful choice making, cultivating and developing good habits suitable for the environment and the society at large.

As Home Economists, the watch words are Reduce, Reuse and Recycle {3Rs}. The goal of this concept is to consciously make efforts to reduce wastes in consumptions of material and human resources, reuse those resources that can be re-used while at the same time, re-cycle some resources, whenever it is possible.

Strategies for Management Non-Human/ Material Resources

1. Conservation of energy and water: Family members are to consciously use electricity lights when necessary. When gadgets and bulbs are not in use, they should be turned off. It is also advisable to use energy bulbs in homes and offices. This helps to conserve energy and make you spend less on electricity.
2. Grow your own food: Keeping a garden of vegetables, poultry and fish farms within your yard and environment will help not only save a lot of finance for the family but will keep the family members healthier.
3. Avoid disposables and single-use items for instance plastic bags: Instead use re-useable bags like bacco bags. Where a family's income is very scarce, it is better to buy cotton napkins which can easily be washed, dried and re-used instead of spending so much on baby pampers.
4. Avoid impulsive shopping: Budget and plan for shopping, check out for durable items, not ones that will not last for the family members.
5. Have a culture of savings: No matter how meagre the family resources are, it is important that a culture of

savings should be embraced. The savings made can help you out in future.

6. Try as much as possible to avoid debts: Taking credit loans and engaging in hire purchasing keeps the family in financial bondage.
7. Engage in multi-economic ventures. Do not rely only on one source of income. Diversifying your sources of income in an unstable economy is very vital. When one source of income depreciates or closes, the other source will sustain the family needs.

Strategies for Management of Human Resources

1. Set priorities and goals for each day to save time and conserve energy.
2. Start your day early. This will help one to accomplish the set tasks and avoid working under stress.
3. Focus on one task at a time.
4. Delegate and share responsibilities and house chores among family members.
5. Be focused and avoid distractions.
6. Avoid procrastinations. This will help you avoid accumulated on done tasks.
7. Engage in undergoing trainings to acquire new knowledge, abilities and skills.
8. Members of the family should endeavor to be creative in an unstable economy.

Family Health and Lifestyle

Family being the basic unit of the society is responsible for the provision of material resources to her members for healthy living. These include food, clothing, shelter, medical resources among others. The healthy status of the family includes the impact of the healthy status of a family member on other members of the family. Family health therefore is a state in which the family serves as a resource for the daily living and health of its members. It is indeed a state of positive interaction between family members which enable each member to enjoy optimum

physical, mental, social, and spiritual wellbeing. Determinants of family health include the living and working conditions of family members, the physical environment, social environment, education and economic factors, health practices, cultural factors, gender stereotypes and the general lifestyles of members of the family.

A family lifestyle refers to the way that family live and co-exist together daily and the habits and patterns they have as individuals and as part of a family unit. This includes the way a family eats and the exercise they take. Igbo (2011) asserts that they are those collective concepts of what the family considers good, desirable, and proper or bad undesirable and improper, their values as individuals and as a group, entertainment, dressing, and recreation among others. Having sustainable family living in an unstable economy, issues of healthy family living, and lifestyles must be put into consideration and of utmost importance. Sustainable lifestyle therefore entails a healthy lifestyle for the family as a unit and each family member.

A healthy lifestyle is that lifestyle that makes family members feel good, happy, and healthy, have positive values, lengthens lifespan, helps one age gracefully and saves money in an unstable economy.

Strategies for Sustainable Healthy Lifestyle:

1. Taking exercises to maintain good health. For instance, taking 30 minutes' walk daily will keep family members fit and reduce unnecessary expenditures on medical bills.
2. Avoiding luxury living. Trying not to be living in affluence, trying not to compete with other families will make family members live within their income and not operating under financial stress and burden.
3. Eating balanced meals and avoiding junk foods saves money and prevents some diseases. Family members should endeavor to eat more vegetables, fruits and whole grains.
4. A family should make efforts to be in control of stress. Create leisure time,

play indoor and outdoor games, and have good hours of sleep. Stress puts one's body into fight or flight mode all the time. Rest days are also important for physical and mental health.

5. Disregard negative values that will create tension and unhappiness in your life.

Avoid alcohol intake, smoking and other dangerous lifestyles. This will not only keep family members healthy but save family resources.

Family Crisis and Insecurity

One of the social challenges that face sustainable family living in an unstable economy is family crisis coupled with its antecedent insecurity. Family crisis is any situation that upsets the normal functioning of the family and requires a new set of responses to whatever is the stressing factor. Family crisis marks a turning point in family relationships and situations that cause them to cease to function as usual. Family crisis therefore poses a threat to the family structure and organizations. Families in crisis often discover that their usual ways of coping and problem solving suddenly do no longer work out positively hence such families are faced with heightened stress, anxieties and threatened insecurity.

Family crisis may be caused and grouped as follows.

1. *Family situations:* These include divorce, desertion of a parent, unplanned pregnancy, serious illness or accidents, child abuse, rape, retrenchment, illegal drug use, spousal abuse and violence, retirement or change of job, relocation of family, arrival of new baby, death of a family member among others.
2. *Economic situations:* These include sudden or chronic financial depletion that may be due to job loss, a theft of household properties or cash, high medical expenses, and others.
3. *Community situations:* Banditry, kidnappings, herdsman attacks,

- armed robbery, neighborhood riots/ civil protests and disturbances and others leading to displacement of family members. In most cases such families are left stranded in Internally Displaced Person (IDPs) camps without good shelter and food.
4. *Natural situations*: These include perennial floods, fire disasters, earthquakes, hurricanes among others.
- iii. Be patient. Well-functioning families recognize the need for peace-making, patience and consideration while poorly functioning families react with anger and blame game.
 - iv. Be good stress managers: Practice a healthy lifestyle and create relaxation period. Remain optimistic, striving to see a better future without denying the reality at hand.
 - v. Help each family member have high esteem and help them be self-reliant. Praise each other often and encourage the strengths of each person.

Family crisis creates feelings of unhappiness, stress, and insecurity in family members. American Psychological Association defines insecurity as a sense of uncertainty or anxiety about your worth, abilities, skills, and value as a person, conveying the message that you are at risk or in danger of something or someone. It manifests in an individual's overriding feeling of inadequacies, lack of self-confidence, self-esteem, and self-worth, anxious about relationships with others.

To maintain a sustainable family living in the period of family crisis and insecurity entails involvement and participation of every family member in supporting one another and being flexible enough to make the needed change. To adjust to a developmental crisis like that of unplanned pregnancy and arrival of new baby, family members need to adjust family rules and roles to meet the new challenges facing members. They should therefore be willing to adapt to change.

Park (2012) suggested the following guidelines, for families adapting to change:

- i. Accept the hardship: Well-functioning families quickly accept the hardship and use their energy and material resources to meet the challenges.
 - ii. Don't blame each other: Poorly functioning families try to attach the blame to someone inside or outside the family circle. Healthy families see the crisis as a family centered problem hence they work together to find a solution to the problem.
 - iii. Be patient. Well-functioning families recognize the need for peace-making, patience and consideration while poorly functioning families react with anger and blame game.
 - iv. Be good stress managers: Practice a healthy lifestyle and create relaxation period. Remain optimistic, striving to see a better future without denying the reality at hand.
 - v. Help each family member have high esteem and help them be self-reliant. Praise each other often and encourage the strengths of each person.
- Generally, family insecurity may be handled using the following strategies:
- i. Acknowledge the role of insecurity in daily life - It is important you ask yourself how insecurity influences your family members in their communication, jobs, and relationships among others and acknowledge the realities at that time.
 - ii. Assess the source of insecurity - It is important you identify the source of insecurity to seek for intervention. The source could be from past life experiences, relationships among others.
 - iii. Openly communicate the insecurity concern. Inability to communicate this concern leads to isolation and shame. Try and be open to trusted individuals and family members.
 - iv. Focus on positives - People who speak to themselves positively challenge their negative self-talk. The way you talk to yourself and the way you see your future have a positive impact on your insecurity
 - v. Take care of your physical health - Create time for leisure, exercise, get good sleep and endeavor to eat good food. Physical health affects one's mental health.
 - vi. Accept your limitations and celebrate your differences. It is important that you accept what you cannot change and find peace with whatever that makes you uncomfortable.

Food Security and Nutrition

In other to maintain a sustainable family living in an unstable economy, families must battle with the issue of food security and nutrition. Food security according to Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO) exists when all people, always have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food which meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life. Food is a basic need of every household. Access to quality and nutritious meals in a family is very paramount for sustainable family living. A family whose members do not live-in hunger or fear of starvation can be said to have food security. In an unstable economy like we are witnessing in Nigeria today, many families are finding it difficult to eat three balanced meals in a day. The cost of basic stable foods has gone up. The issue of insecurity, herders and farmers crisis has made farmers either not to cultivate their usual hectares of farmland or have lost their farm produce to cows that invade their farms. Perennial flooding in Nigeria due to the overflow of the Cameroonian dam has also contributed to loss of hectares of farm products. In Benue State today, many farmers due to banditry has been displaced from their ancestral homes and thereby have been living in Internally Displaced People camps. This is also the case in most food producing States in Nigeria. This has led to shortage of food production, increase in cost of food production, and increase in food price. Food security therefore is linked to poverty level of families.

Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations identified four pillars of food security to include: availability, access, utilization, and stability. Food insecurity occurs in families when a household or family members' lack predictable access to foods in sufficient quantity and quality to enable them to maintain active and healthy lifestyles. Abraham, Lund, Field and Honikman (2018) affirm that it is when the availability of nutritionally adequate and safe foods or the ability to acquire acceptable foods in an acceptable way is limited or uncertain.

The issue of food security has been a thing of concern to many nations and Nigeria inclusive. To alleviate the problem of food insecurity, the Nigerian government sometimes releases grains from the national grain reserves across the country. This however has been observed to make little or no significant positive effect on Nigerian families. The United State Department of Agriculture (USDA) defined food insecurity as a situation of limited or uncertain availability of nutritionally adequate and safe foods or limited or uncertain ability to acquire acceptable foods in socially acceptable ways.

In 1996, World Summit on Food Security declared that food should not be used as instrument for political and economic pressure. Hence both individuals, religious bodies, governments at all levels should cooperatively fight the problem of food insecurity in the nation and at the household level. Specifically, the following strategies can help.

Strategies for Enhancing Food Security and Nutrition

- i. Cultivate and harvest farm produce grown at your local farms
- ii. Make storage facilities available to preserve food items when in season.
- iii. Family members should focus in eating balanced meals with lots of vegetables and fruits. This will curb malnutrition in families.
- iv. Be kind to the less privilege. Distribute food to families facing hunger.
- v. Insecurity is directly related to poverty. The government should embark on poverty alleviation programs that will create wealth for family members to achieve food security.
- vi. Government should empower both peasant and industrial farmers to make them go into large scale farming.
- vii. Farmers should be given adequate security to protect their farms from been invaded or destroyed by cows in the name of open grazing policies.

- viii. There should be accessibility of good road network and secure and efficient transportation system for farmers to convey their produce for sales for economic and national development.
- ix. Credit facilities should be given to small and medium scale farmers with minimal interest to assist them enlarge their production capacities.
- x. The government should encourage the creation of large farms which will contribute to the development of local markets and reduction in the rate of urbanization.
- xi. The government should cooperate with other countries so that she can obtain necessary technology, knowledge and means of production. International humanitarian aids should also be encouraged to continue their aids to Nigerian farmers such like USAID office of Food for Peace (FFP) that has been providing emergency food assistance to Nigeria since 2015.

Ibori (2018) summarized the following solutions to food security in Nigeria as:

- i. The development of sustainable food markets.
- ii. Technical re-equipment of agricultural enterprises.
- iii. Improving the competitiveness of products.
- iv. Improvement of land relations.

Achieving the goals of food security in Nigeria will help maintain employment and create new jobs, increase income, improve health, and ultimately raise the level and quality of life of the citizenry.

Covid-19 Pandemic and Family Adjustment

Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) has ravaged many countries across the globe. Covid-19 is an illness caused by a novel Coronavirus which was first identified amid an outbreak of respiratory illness cases in Wuhan City, Hubei province, China. It was

initially reported to the World Health Organization (WHO) on December 31, 2019. On January 30, 2020 WHO declared Covid-19 outbreak a global pandemic.

A pandemic is a disease or an epidemic of infectious disease that spread across multiple continents and regions. The Covid-19 pandemic has affected many nations and families negatively. Some countries closed their borders, healthcare services were over stretched, schools were closed, and human beings were quarantined while some other people went on self-isolation from public view and in some cases from family members. The incidence of Covid-19 therefore brought forth many things that call for adjustments in various homes. For instance, family economic bases were short changed. Bread winners who supposed to be doing business, such business outfits were locked down, pupils stopped going to physical schools, few were schooling online, religious activities were also locked up, families who were fond of attending such religious meetings could no longer attend physically and many were forced to be attending online church services. Beloved members of the family who died due to Covid-19 or just died during the period were either not given the usual glamorous burial rites by family members or were just buried by the State governments. Many family members felt isolated, anxious, bored and feelings of uncertainty filled the air. Family members got to understand that the usual time they spend in workplaces, churches, sporting activities and other recreational events are no longer available. Life changed due to Covid-19 and its effect on social distancing, quarantine, isolation and new looks with different shapes and colors of face and nose masks that is very inconveniencing and uncomfortable for sustainable family living. It is indeed a traumatic period that came with adjustment problems.

Adjustment is the reactions to demand pressures of social environment imposed upon the individual. Psychologists view adjustment in two ways - Adjustment as achievement and adjustment as a process. As an achievement, adjustment is viewed as

how efficiently an individual can perform his duties under different circumstances. And as a process, adjustment is perceived as a process by which an individual copes with his eternal environment (Edugyan, 2017).

During this Covid-19 era, families should make efforts to cope with the pandemic in several ways with the focus to reducing its spread and stress and sustaining healthy family living.

Strategies for Adjusting to Covid-19 Pandemic

1. **Maintain basic hygiene:** To curtail the spread of the Corona Virus Disease, family members should maintain basic hygiene of washing hands with soap under running water for at least twenty seconds. They should also comply with the rule of wearing face and nose masks and ensure they maintain physical and social distancing when interacting with people outside the family.
2. **Stock up your food store:** It is important that each family plans for sustainable family living by stocking up their food store. Covid-19 came with lock down, in such case; it was only families that had food in stock that were able to cope adequately. Plan your shopping to reduce trips outside your home environment and also pick some easy-to - make meals in case members become very sick.
3. **Be happy and kind:** In case you contact Covid-19, be kind to others and to yourself by getting into isolation in order not to infect other individuals. Be thoughtful, share your resources and keep yourself happy. You can practice guided meditation, breathing exercise, and staying in touch with family members and friends. Such practices will give you a healthy outlook and you remain a strong support for yourself.
4. **Have online classes, lessons, and teachings for the educational development of family members.** In so doing, family members who are in schools will still cover their syllabus and have their tests and examinations. Families may also stream educational documentaries; download some audio books among others.
5. **Pick up a hobby:** Adjust to the Covid-19 period time to venture into new hobbies and new skills. This will not only keep you out of breakdown but keep you mentally sound and alert.
6. **Handling unemployment:** Covid-19 pandemic period indeed brought unemployment to some family members thus affecting their earning capacity. Such families should seek for new employment even as they develop entrepreneurial skills that will put them back on income earning.
7. **The period also calls for online trading, shopping, and participation in other business ventures.** Some trades can now be done online instead of the physical travelling and having physical contacts with many people in physical markets.
8. **Zoom meetings and video conferencing is an emergence of Covid-19 in an unstable economy.** In other to avoid much physical contact, spending monies on travels, family members can now engage in organizing and participating in zoom meetings and video conferencing activities.

Trends in Fashion and Sustainable Clothing Innovation

Fashion is a popular or the latest style of clothing, hair decoration, accessories, furniture, or behavior. It is also a manner of doing things and area of activity that involves styles of clothing and appearance. Fashion trends may be influenced by fashion forecast, celebrities, movies and music, fashion stylist, nation's economy, technology among others. A family's socio-economic

status most often determines the quality, style, cost, and trend of fashion they choose.

In early 70s, 80s and even 90s many family members were purchasing more expensive clothing's like Holland is, Ghana Prints, English Wax, English suits, foreign wigs and Italian shoes among others. The unstable economic situations across the globe have forced many fabric and fashion industries to shut down. This is not different in Nigeria. Many textile factories in the country have collapsed and have been shut down prominent among them is the Nigerian Nichem factory; many other industries are closing their stores and canceling orders. Many high-income family members now avoid ostentatious living but dressing simply in Nigerian Ankara materials; knowing that ostentatious costume is in bad taste in these days of unstable economy. Many families especially the young ladies have resorted to make do with their meager resources to mend and shop for secondhand clothes.

Unstable economy has introduced innovations in the clothing industries. Innovation is the creation, development and implementation of a new product, process, or service, with the aim of improving efficiency, effectiveness, or competitive advantage. It is an idea that has been transformed into practical reality. In the clothing industry, technology has been introduced in the production of fabrics, designs, styles, and color mix thereby giving rise to unique innovations. Fashion technology is the newest innovation in the fashion industry that enables one to have a unique experience when you wear fabrics made of it or interact with it. Other innovations include-virtual clothes, fashion blockchain, 3D printed sustainable fashion, nanotechnology materials, bio packaging, needle free sewing, extraction of fibers from oranges and apples, knitting robots, laboratory made fabrics and others. Behr (2018) added fashion wearable and smart clothes as part of innovations in clothing industries.

The fashion industry has also been boosted using internet which has proved undesirable to the growth of fashion

business. Innovative fashion therefore allows designers to function and interact in a digital world to remain relevant in the fashion business.

In addition, young graduates and entrepreneurs use internet to project design, mix colors, invite and attract customers through advertisements on social media like Facebook, WhatsApp, and Twitter among others. Hill and Lee (2015) noted that the growth of fast fashions has made clothes much cheaper, relative to income in comparison to a few decades ago.

To be able to keep fit into modern fashion trends and sustainable clothing innovation, family members can key into the following strategies:

1. In an unstable economy, family members who do not have much should still operate in the principle of repair, reuse, make do and don't throw away anything. The concept of repair, reuse, make do and don't waste anything gives room to a lot of creative fashion that does not only make one look good but saves cost.
2. Use cheaper or less costly fabrics and sew great styles out of it. Nigerian fabrics like Ankara can be used against Hollandis from Holland.
3. Family members can engage in renovating their clothes. Renovation is the process of repairing, renewing, or restoring to good condition by making old clothes to look new. Individuals can use unwanted fabrics to make new clothes to extend the life of the clothes.
4. Ladies can braid long lasting hairs and carry it for a period against the previous tradition of braiding hairs weekly. This not only saves cost but time.
5. Gold jewelries have given way to our Nigerian beads, English gold with fewer carats, low necklaces than the long gold chains.
6. Nigerian made hats have taken over the English hats. Ladies now go on handmade auto-gele that comes in various shapes, colors, and styles.

Conclusion

Most national economies have been plagued with depression, recession, or instability as is the case of Nigeria. Although the society is also ravaged with a lot of social challenges threatening sustainable living of most family households, the paper has identified some strategies that will assist family members cope and adjust to the identified changes and challenges. The paper therefore believes that following the identified strategies, family members will live happy, healthy, and fulfilling lives.

References

- Abrahams, Z; Lund, C; Field, S. & Honikman, S. (2018). Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol. 53(4), 363-372.- factors associated with household food insecurity and depression in Pregnant South African Women from a low social-economic setting: a cross sectional study.
- Behr, O. (2018). Fashion 4.0 digital innovation in the fashion industry. Retrieved June 19, 2021, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326263764_Fashion_4.0_-_Digital_Innovation_in_the_Fashion_Industry
- Brennan, D. (2020). Signs of Insecurity. Retrieved 12/06/2021 from <https://www.weband.com/mental-health/signs-insecurity>
- Edugyan, (2017). Adjustment and maladjustment: Characteristics and causes. Retrieved June 5, 2021, from www.edugyan.in/2017/03/adjust.
- Hill, J. & Lee, H.-H. (2015), Sustainable brand extensions of fast fashion retailers. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*. 19 (2), 205-222.
- Ibori, D. (2018). Solutions to food Security in Nigeria. Nigeria News - Ask Legit. Retrieved July 15, 2021 from <https://www.legit.ng/1134799-Solutions-food-insecurity-nigeria.html>.
- Igbo, H. I. (2011). Re-orientation of unhealthy values and lifestyles in Nigerian families. *Journal of Home Economics Research*. 14, 303-309.
- Park, E (2012). Surviving a Family Crisis in P.T Nelson (Ed) Families Maller. A Newsletter Series for Parents of School Age Youth. Newark, DE: Cooperative Extension, University of Delaware.